

Managers' work context-related unwell-being: A study on the largest businesses in Turkey

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Abstract: The aim of this study is to capture and scrutinize the nature of managers' unwell-being through an original integrative research model in order to find out how this unwell-being is structured when the four prominent unwell-being factors, namely absenteeism, job alienation, job dissatisfaction, and presenteeism are accounted for. To enable generalizations at the national level, we contacted mid-level managers of the 500 largest businesses of Turkey. A professional consulting firm used our developed questionnaires to collect data from these managers. The two-phase research process pointed out that the model was realistic; there were indeed interactions among all the mentioned unwell-being factors. Further investigations revealed that the three of these factors (presenteeism, job alienation, and absenteeism) had strong and positive connections; whereas the fourth, job dissatisfaction, could pose very weak and negative interactions with the others. We believe that the integrative approach used is the unique contribution of this study as there are theoretical and practical gaps regarding the unwell-being research that consider an aggregation of multiple factors simultaneously.

JEL Classifications: M12, M10

Keywords: Absenteeism, job alienation, job dissatisfaction, presenteeism, Turkey

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1. Introduction

The business context cannot be properly considered without discussing people. With this in mind, the current study targets one specific group of people, managers, because they are one of the most important assets of any business (Tymon & Stumpf, 2003), and they are the key determinants of many business issues (Ali, Rehman, Ali, Yousaf, & Zia, 2010).

There is a clear shift towards knowledge and competency in many postmodern paradigms, and this shift imposes a burden on managers and other business members, which introduces the issue of their well-being (Kocel, 2015). Well-being is a vital part of the organizational behavior literature, and there are countless related factors in the work context. A brief, incomplete list could include job satisfaction (Robbins, De Cenzo, & Judge, 2012), job alienation (Hirschfeld & Feild, 2000), empowerment (Carmeli, Atwater, & Levi, 2011), organizational culture (Schein, 2004), absenteeism (Cucchiella, Gastaldi, & Ranieri, 2014), presenteeism (Hyman, Baldry, Scholarios, & Bunzel, 2003) and conflict (Aksoy & Kaplan, 2005), in addition to many issues that relate to management (Petrescu & Simmons, 2008), leadership (Sullivan, 2012), and organizational structure (Liao, Chuang, & To, 2011).

A key observational fact is the interconnectedness among these factors; there is enough proof in the literature that they are tied to one another (e.g., Bowers, Hall, & Srinivasan, 2017). The dyadic nature of these ties, however, makes it impossible to capture well-being

thoroughly, although there have been some faint efforts to consider multiple connections among multiple factors simultaneously (e.g., Ayrançi & Ertuğrul Ayrançi, 2017).

This bottleneck is the main driver behind the consideration of well-being in this study. If the goal is to discern the truth about well-being, then it is not logical to consider a sole indicator. A better solution would require using multiple indicators with many embedded points of view. That is, an investigation of well-being cannot be limited to any single factor mentioned thus far, and a combination of these factors should be used for a multifaceted approach.

This logic, however, has a great drawback. There is no consensus as to the most appropriate method for selecting among the well-being-related factors mentioned or relating these factors to one another. This necessitates the identification of a leading concept for managers' work context-related well-being, which should also have well-grounded and proved relationships with other well-being-related factors. A literature review with this in mind leads to the factor of presenteeism.

The use of an integrative model that not only involves presenteeism at its heart but also considers the existence of many other well-being-related factors, along with their simultaneous connections to one another and presenteeism, would overcome the problem of a unilateral or partial focus on managers' well-being. The related literature, however, reveals that there is a great gap regarding this integrative model.

A final prompt for this current study is the intrinsic nature of presenteeism. Despite the multifariousness of the mentioned well-being-related factors, each emphasizes a specific financial, physical, psychological, social, or organizational aspect. Presenteeism, to the contrary, is a multi-aspect concept that embraces these aspects simultaneously.

Therefore, this study proposes a unique integrative model that examines managers' well-being via presenteeism and some other selected well-being-related factors that involve job alienation, absenteeism, and job dissatisfaction. The model development is performed based not only on the mentioned reasons and the literature but also on the fact that all considered factors are on the negative horizon of well-being. Thus, it is convenient to say that this study scrutinizes the interactions among the selected factors of managers' unwell-being in relation to their work context. Because the participants are the mid-level managers of the 500 largest businesses in Turkey as of 2018 (Istanbul Chamber of Industry, 2019), this study also maintains an awareness of the trends of business management in Turkey.

The next section includes the literature review with the aim of introducing the four underlying unwell-being factors, along with an intention of discussing their connections. While the third section clarifies the aim and design of the research, results of the pilot and main studies are presented in the fourth section. Finally, the fifth section provides details about limitations of the research, and concluding remarks and related discussions are made in the last section.

2. Literature review

Business scholars' contemporary interest in presenteeism dates to the early 2000s (e.g., Chatterji & Tilley, 2002), and this interest is evident in both management (e.g., Worrall, Cooper, & Campbell, 2000) and occupational health (e.g., Koopman et al., 2002) studies.

Currently, presenteeism is a central topic in a vast variety of business contexts (Janssens et al., 2016).

The gradual emergence of some related concepts has given rise to a rigorous questioning of presenteeism. For example, the 1970s (Smithy, 1970) and 1980s (Proctor & Ditton, 1989) witnessed the first debates about the relationships between presenteeism and absenteeism. In the 1990s, the presenteeism literature flourished, and studies rigorously investigated the premises of presenteeism (Cooper & Cartwright, 1994) and its outcomes (French & Zarkin, 1998) and remedies (Cooper & Cartwright, 1994). In the 2000s, perspectives regarding presenteeism began to be fit together, which enabled the formation of relatively general approaches.

Unfortunately, the emergence of these general approaches was not a guarantee of a consensus about presenteeism's definition. However, a simple definition put forward by Cooper (1998) proposes that presenteeism could be considered to be business members' fallacious behaviors that they have worked or have been working too long to continue. This is an operational definition, although it lacks any rationale as to why presenteeism might occur. The explanatory pitfall is addressed by many other definitions, and some of these definitions refer to physical conditions. For instance, Bierla, Huver, & Richard (2013) frame presenteeism as being unwillingly present in the workplace due to sickness.

This and other similar definitions have become a major point of discussion in the literature as the unilateral focus on health is posited to offer an incomplete rationale for presenteeism (Baysal, Baysal, Aksu, & Aksu, 2014). This has led to the expansion of reasons for presenteeism, which has caused the consideration of a multifactor presenteeism construct. Chatterji & Tilley (2002) describe presenteeism, the unwillingness to work while being present in the workplace, as the combined result of a perceived negative business psycho-social atmosphere and poor physical conditions. Patel, Budhwar, & Varma (2012) share a similar paradigm and designate presenteeism as the result of business members' perceptions of an obligation to work despite their unwillingness due to the unfavorable effect of the organizational culture along with some personal health problems. As understood, psycho-social issues play a vital role in presenteeism.

Although one direction of definitions expands towards health and psycho-social issues, another direction moves towards personal goals and achievements. Loeppke et al. (2003) treat presenteeism as business members' use of time without addressing their business-related tasks in the workplace because of their desire to take more time for their own individual goals. D'Abate & Eddy (2007) argue that presenteeism is simply a waste of time because it is the engagement with personal matters in the workplace. This approach is further supported by some cognitive-based claims. For example, Gilbreath & Karimi (2012) consider presenteeism to be working at a very low productivity level due to the use of one's own cognitive resources to perform personal tasks.

As discussed above, presenteeism is a convenient concept to use to scrutinize managers' unwell-being due to its intrinsic nature, variety of premises, and connections to many other unwell-being related factors. Although some causes have already been identified in discussions of the definitions of presenteeism, a closer look reveals that the causes could be grouped into the three categories of job-related factors, attitudes, and personal factors (Hansen & Andersen, 2008).

One of the most obvious factors behind presenteeism is fear. When business members consider reporting their illness, they may perceive an intensifying threat to their positions

in terms of losing their current jobs (Lewis & Cooper, 1995) or missing opportunities regarding future potential promotions (Caverley, Cunningham, & MacGregor, 2007). This perceived threat grows when business members' substitutability potential is high (McTernan, Dollard, & LaMontagne, 2013), when distributional justice is poor (Janssens et al., 2016), or when there is substantial understaffing (Deery, Walsh, & Zatzick, 2014).

Altruism is also considered, as business members could conclude that their illnesses could create an additional burden on their colleagues, and they therefore may feel the obligation to stay and work despite their illnesses (Grinyer & Singleton, 2000). Similarly, another altruistic issue could be one's love for his or her job. Business members may love to perform their business tasks and consequently choose to work despite their illnesses (Johns & Nicholson, 1982).

Organizational factors include a discouraging organizational culture (Laing & Jones, 2016), psychological or even physical abuse in the workplace (Kivimaki et al., 2003), low management support (Zhou, Martinez, Ferreira, & Rodrigues, 2016), poor physical working conditions (Hayta, 2007), and ineffective human resources and career policies (Janssens et al., 2016).

A related factor to presenteeism is job dissatisfaction, which leads to performance losses at both the individual and organizational levels (Eginli, 2009). The main connective agent between presenteeism and job dissatisfaction is *unwillingness* (Ceylan, 1998); it has been asserted that business members' physical presence along with their chronic psycho-emotional unwillingness to be present, i.e., presenteeism, leads to gradual increases in job dissatisfaction (Karanika-Murray, Pontes, Griffiths, & Biron, 2015). This assertion has yet to be tested, as there is very little and mixed evidence in the literature. For instance, some results show very weak (Caverley, Cunningham, & MacGregor, 2007) or moderate (Karanika-Murray, Pontes, Griffiths, & Biron, 2015) relationships between presenteeism and job dissatisfaction, while other findings suggest the nonexistence of such relationships (Cocker, Martin, Scott, Venn, & Sanderson, 2013).

Interestingly, there is disagreement about cause and effect relationships. Presenteeism and job dissatisfaction are considered to have bilateral relationships (Caverley, Cunningham, & MacGregor, 2007), job dissatisfaction is claimed to affect presenteeism (Aronsson & Gustafsson, 2005), and presenteeism is posited to have an effect on job dissatisfaction (Karanika-Murray, Pontes, Griffiths, & Biron, 2015).

Absenteeism is another prominent related factor. Absenteeism is when a business member chooses to leave a job temporarily due to his or her own perception that the workplace and tasks are either stressful or unfair, despite being healthy (Bierla, Huver, & Richard, 2013), or when a worker chooses to leave temporarily simply due to being ill (Bergström, Bodin, Hagberg, Aronsson, & Josephson, 2009). Therefore, absenteeism for reasons other than illness implies the presence of psycho-social factors (Johns, 2010).

Absenteeism is also considered to be an alternative to presenteeism (Aronsson & Gustafsson, 2005). Therefore, some scholars (e.g., Deery, Walsh, & Zatzick, 2014), posit that absenteeism is actually a defense mechanism against presenteeism: the business member simply chooses to be absent to avoid potentially irreversible harm after challenging the norm of presenteeism and in the end, fails (Bergström, Bodin, Hagberg, Aronsson, & Josephson, 2009). This suggests that presenteeism may result in absenteeism. Nevertheless, this suggestion has yet to be supported by sound evidence (Gosselin, Lemyre, & Corneil, 2013). An in-depth literature review shows that this evidence partly

exists for the case of mild physical or mental illness. The business member is indecisive and at first, fluctuates between presenteeism or absenteeism (Johns, 2010), and the decision for presenteeism results in toleration of the illness to a certain degree until excessive discomfort boosts his or her unwillingness to work, which leads to absenteeism (Gustafsson & Marklund, 2011).

The last factor to be considered is job alienation. This phenomenon is expressed as a decrease in a business member's consideration of himself or herself, colleagues, other people, and the environment due to the perceived limitations of his or her own creativity or initiative in the workplace (Fromm, 1991). The three pillars of job alienation, i.e., powerlessness, meaninglessness, and self-estrangement (Mottaz, 1981), illustrate the possible connections of job alienation to presenteeism. An investigation of these connections provides support: presenteeism is a cause of job alienation due to the central role of one's own unwillingness (Göncü & Metin, 2018). More precisely, the continuation of a business member's unwillingness to be present in the workplace gradually results in attention shifts from business issues to personal issues; therefore, business-related matters and people are perceived as unnecessary, burdensome elements, which leads to the alienation of the business member (Floderus, Göransson, Alexanderson, & Aronsson, 2005).

3. Methods/Data

As mentioned before, the main aim of this research is to investigate the interactions among the selected factors of managers' work context-related unwell-being by using a unique integrative model. The literature review suggested starting with presenteeism as the first of such factors, and the evidence about its connections to other unwell-being factors urged the inclusion of job alienation, absenteeism, and job dissatisfaction. The model is depicted in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1. THE RESEARCH MODEL

Source: Own.

It could be stated that the aforesaid aim had a profound extent on the grounds that it overarched the aforementioned dyadic ties, used an original integrative approach, and shed light on managers' unwell-being, which is a topic rarely considered in the literature. These reasons necessitated a thorough investigation.

Therefore, it was considered that the sample had to sufficiently represent the Turkish business context in terms of the subject. As a result, many subsequent steps were taken for sampling. There are countless businesses in this context, but fortunately, a list of the largest businesses in Turkey is prepared each year by the Istanbul Chamber of Industry via a specific methodology that uses a combination of financial criteria along with the number of employees. The latest list for the largest 500 businesses in Turkey was prepared for 2018 (Istanbul Chamber of Industry, 2019), and this list was obtained to identify the target businesses. In the next step, a consulting firm was contracted to identify the mid-level managers within each business where possible. This firm attempted to access these managers' e-mail addresses and phone extensions. The outcome was a database that contained 12,853 e-mails and 2,484 extensions.

The data collection method was the application of questionnaires, and it was vital to reach as many participants as possible. Another sensitive issue was the use of two-stage research; there had to be a pilot study to determine the aforementioned factors' structures and a main study to test the research model denoted in Figure 1.

Before starting with the data collection process, a two-phase approach was used to obtain the confirmations of managers for their participation. All managers in the database were e-mailed. The e-mails included brief information about the study, the authors, the firm, and a polite request for their consent to participate. The e-mails were then resent to the recipients who had not answered after two weeks. After waiting for another two weeks for their replies, the mailing phase was finally over. In the second phase, the consulting firm phoned the managers who had never replied to any e-mails sent and whose e-mail addresses were unreachable. This phase lasted for a week. The ultimate result was 2,629 volunteers. It was decided to conduct the pilot study with 263 participants (10% of the total) and spare the rest for the main study (2,366 participants) to avoid double counting. Questionnaires were applied by the consulting firm by using three methods where applicable, namely, e-mailing, telephone surveying, and physical distribution and collection if needed.

Given the aim of the research, the questionnaires involved the four dimensions of presenteeism, job dissatisfaction, job alienation, and absenteeism. Presenteeism was measured on Koopman et al.'s (2002) Stanford Presenteeism Scale, which solely considers physical health problems. As a multifaceted approach was embraced, this scale was extended to include other factors. The extension was made by rewording the original items of the scale to problems in the work context and problems related to the job itself. Therefore, health, the work context, and job issues were in the scope of the extended instrument, which would be examined in terms of its statistical structure and reliability. Job dissatisfaction was measured through the negatively reworded items of many scales from Brayfield & Rothe (1951), Hackman & Oldham (1974), Jamal & Baba (2000), and Nadler, Jenkins, Cammann, & Lawler (1975).

Finally, job alienation was considered according to the eight-item scale of Nair & Vohra (2010), and absenteeism was addressed through the six-item Rijeka Absenteeism Scale developed by Lalic & Hromin (2012) and the related items of the Workplace Outcome Suite that was validated by Lennox, Sharar, Goehner, & Shmitz (2018). All items were strictly translated into Turkish and then checked and corrected by professional Turkish instructors for grammar and meaning.

4. Results

4.1. Pilot study: statistical structures and reliabilities

The pilot study was conducted with 263 participants, and the intent was to achieve proper and reliable statistical structures. Investigations were conducted by the application of exploratory factor analyses because the instruments used had not been previously fully tested in the Turkish context and required the rewording and translation of items. The common criteria of exploratory factor analyses included principle components analysis, varimax rotation, and suppression of factor loadings less than $|0.5|$. The reliability of all items and the items in each respective factor were checked via the Cronbach's alpha method.

TABLE 1. RESULTS OF THE EXPLORATORY FACTOR AND RELIABILITY ANALYSES OF PRESENTEEISM

KMO Value: 0.777 (Bartlett's test value is significant at 5%).				
Cronbach's Alpha Value: 0.761		Variance Explained (%) : 17.389	Cronbach's Alpha Value: 0.738	
		Factor Loading	Variance Explained (%) : 15.941	
Work and Job Context - Negativity (P_WJC_N)			Work and Job Context - Resistance (P_WJC_R)	
				Factor Loading
QP15. I cannot sufficiently enjoy my job due to the problems with my work context.		0.787	QP17. I focus on my professional career goals despite the problems with my work context.	0.811
QP13. I have difficulties coping with my business-related stress due to the problems with my work context.		0.771	QP14. I still accomplish difficult tasks in my business despite the problems with my work context.	0.785
QP19. I have difficulties coping with my business-related stress due to the problems regarding my job itself.		0.704	QP18. I still find the energy to fulfill all my duties despite the problems with my work context.	0.745
QP16. I even have difficulties in carrying out my daily business tasks due to the problems with my work context.		0.664	QP23. I focus on my professional career targets despite the problems regarding my job itself.	0.577
QP21. I cannot relish my job enough due to the problems regarding my job itself.		0.569		
Cronbach's Alpha Value: 0.781		Variance Explained (%) : 13.912	Cronbach's Alpha Value: 0.765	
		Factor Loading	Variance Explained (%) : 13.544	
Physical Health - Negativity (P_PH_N)			Physical Health - Resistance (P_PH_R)	
				Factor Loading
QP3. I cannot sufficiently enjoy my job due to my physical health problems.		0.817	QP6. I still find the energy to fulfill all my duties despite my physical health problems.	0.865
QP4. I even have difficulties in carrying out my daily business tasks due to my physical health problems.		0.776	QP5. I focus on my professional career targets despite my physical health problems.	0.862
QP1. I have difficulties in coping with my business-related stress due to my physical health problems.		0.717	QP2. I still accomplish difficult tasks in my business despite my physical health problems.	0.661

Source: Own calculations.

Note: The items have been reworded and were originally translated into Turkish.

To start with, presenteeism was considered first. The results are shown in Table 1. Four factors emerged that explained 60.786% of the total variance. The Cronbach's alpha of all items was 0.753.

Table 1 suggests a unique composition of presenteeism. There are actually two main groups of fragments - Work and Job Context and Physical Health. An interesting outcome is that these fragments are bidirectional; they both have a negative effect on the participants *and* are challenged by the participants. In addition to the structure's originality, it is consistent with the results reported in the literature. The domain of presenteeism involves the managers' personal factors, attitudes, and job/business-related factors as discussed earlier. The dualistic nature of presenteeism - being in the workplace and performing tasks, albeit with a great unwillingness - can also be clearly seen.

The next subject was job alienation; Table 2 shows that it comprised two factors with 65.959% of the variance explained. The overall reliability level was 0.902.

TABLE 2. RESULTS OF THE EXPLORATORY FACTOR AND RELIABILITY ANALYSES OF JOB ALIENATION

	Job Alienation	
	Business Oriented (JA_BO)	Task Oriented (JA_TO)
KMO Value: 0.904 (Bartlett's test value is significant at 5%).		
Variance Explained (%)	39.742	26.217
Cronbach's Alpha Value	0.926	0.887
QJA5. I do not feel any commitment towards events in my business.	0.847	
QJA6. I feel distanced from my business.	0.831	
QJA4. Facing my responsibilities in my business is difficult and unrewarding.	0.827	
QJA7. I do not enjoy working in this business; I only work to earn money.	0.804	
QJA3. I wish I were working in another business.	0.801	
QJA8. I have had disappointments with my tasks over the years.		0.812
QJA2. I do not have a feeling of accomplishment regarding my tasks.		0.798
QJA1. Tasking is more like menial labor or a burden to me.		0.771

Source: Own calculations.

Note: The items have been reworded and were originally translated into Turkish.

The dual-factor structure, which is obtained from Table 2, points out that job alienation concerns the business itself and the tasks performed. The participants stated that they were unwilling to be in their current businesses and that they were bored with their tasks.

According to Table 3, absenteeism is also a two-factor issue much like job alienation. Although these factors accounted for 64.271% of the total variance, the overall reliability level was 0.861.

Table 3 presents the core of absenteeism: taking sick leave and not attending to work properly. It is noteworthy that the structure of absenteeism addresses both personal and work-related issues simultaneously.

The last subject, job dissatisfaction, also comprised two factors with an overall 71.139% of the variance explained and a high reliability level (Cronbach's Alpha: 0.862) according to Table 4.

TABLE 3. RESULTS OF THE EXPLORATORY FACTOR AND RELIABILITY ANALYSES OF ABSENTEEISM

	Absenteeism	
	Personal Issues (A_PI)	Work-Related Issues (A_WRI)
KMO Value: 0.667 (Bartlett's test value is significant at 5%).		
Variance Explained (%)	41.852	22.419
Cronbach's Alpha Value	0.889	0.825
QA7. I left work early frequently due to my personal problems in the last 30 days.	0.875	
QA6. I was late to work frequently due to my personal problems in the last 30 days.	0.862	
QA9. I frequently missed my work entirely due to my personal problems in the last 30 days.	0.793	
QA4. I only take sick-leave if I am truly unable to work.		0.803
QA3. I can take sick-leave to get a little rest.		0.789
QA5. I can take sick-leave if it is related to work, although it is not necessary.		0.724

Source: Own calculations.

Note: The items have been reworded and were originally translated into Turkish.

TABLE 4. RESULTS OF THE EXPLORATORY FACTOR AND RELIABILITY ANALYSES OF JOB DISSATISFACTION

	Job Dissatisfaction	
	Job and Task Challenges (JD_JTC)	Equality Problems (JD_E)
KMO Value: 0.744 (Bartlett's test value is significant at 5%).		
Variance Explained (%)	39.138	32.001
Cronbach's Alpha Value	0.913	0.897
Q5JD. I do not like the job that I do.	0.924	
Q3JD. The tasks that I do in my job are not as important as my personal tasks.	0.915	
Q2JD. The workload at my business is very high.	0.822	
Q7JD. Most of my time is spent on activities that are not required by my job.	0.759	
Q9JD. I do not work under the same conditions as my peers in this business.		0.911
Q12JD. I am not sufficiently supported by my business in financial and nonfinancial terms.		0.867
Q11JD. Business resources are not equally distributed among managers.		0.731

Source: Own calculations.

Note: The items have been reworded and were originally translated into Turkish.

As indicated in Table 4, job dissatisfaction is a general discontent about the participants' jobs and tasks and the way that they are being treated within the business context.

At this point, the pilot study could be concluded with the considerations that all subjects that fall into the domain of unwell-being posed multifactor structures, abided by the general ideas voiced in the literature, and emphasized both personal and work context-related issues. The pilot study was performed with the data collected from 263 participants out of a total of 2,629 people. In the next step, the main study proceeded to the

questionnaires that were optimized according to the outcomes of the pilot study and involved the rest of the participants, specifically, 2,366 mid-level managers.

4.2. Main study: structure confirmations

The main study comprised two stages. In the first stage, all statistical structures were tested to determine whether they could still be confirmed. For this purpose, a second-level factor modeling was used for each distinct construct by using structural equation modeling. The last stage was the analysis of the research model, again, by using the same approach while preserving the confirmed structures.

As there are four constructs, it was decided to exhibit their confirmations two-by-two to save space. Therefore, presenteeism and absenteeism were primarily considered. Figure 2 shows their second-level factor modeling along with the t-values. An instant result was that both constructs are valid.

FIGURE 2. SECOND-LEVEL FACTOR MODELING FOR PRESENTEEISM AND ABSENTEEISM WITH t-VALUES

Note: **PRESENT**: Presenteeism; **P_WJC_N**: Work and Job Context - Negativity; **P_WJC_R**: Work and Job Context - Resistance; **P_PH_N**: Physical Health - Negativity; **P_PH_R**: Physical Health - Resistance; **ABS**: Absenteeism; **A_PI**: Personal Issues; **A_WRI**: Work-Related Issues. Please see Tables 1 and 3 for the item abbreviations.

Source: Own calculations.

The next step required a check of the overall health of these two models; therefore, their goodness-of-fit statistics were investigated. The results given in Table 5 exhibit that there is no problem regarding their factuality if the foremost statistics are in question.

TABLE 5. GOODNESS-OF-FIT STATISTICS FOR THE PRESENTEEISM AND ABSENTEEISM CONSTRUCTS

CRITERION	ACCEPTED LIMITS*	VALUES	RESULT
RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation)	Good fit: $RMSEA < 0.05$	Presenteeism: 0.067	Acceptable fit.
	Acceptable fit: $0.05 \leq RMSEA \leq 0.1$	Absenteeism: 0.060	Acceptable fit.
GFI (Goodness of Fit Index)	Good fit: $0.95 \leq GFI \leq 1.00$	Presenteeism: 0.93	Acceptable fit.
	Acceptable fit: $0.9 < GFI < 0.95$	Absenteeism: 0.98	Good fit.
AGFI (Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index)	Good fit: $0.95 \leq AGFI \leq 1.00$	Presenteeism: 0.91	Acceptable fit.
	Acceptable fit: $0.9 < AGFI < 0.95$	Absenteeism: 0.99	Good fit.
CFI (Comparative Fit Index)	$0.90 \leq CFI$	Presenteeism: 0.94	Good fit.
		Absenteeism: 0.97	Good fit.
SRMR (Standardized Root Mean Square Residual)	SRMR < 0.05	Presenteeism: 0.094	Unacceptable fit.
		Absenteeism: 0.059	Unacceptable fit.

Note: * Diamantopoulos & Siguaw (2000); Schermelleh-Engel, Moosbrugger, & Müller (2003).

As each aforementioned construct proved itself, it was decided to scrutinize their structural equations to distinctively comment on managers' ideas about presenteeism and absenteeism. This was achieved by monitoring the outcome in Table 6.

TABLE 6. STRUCTURAL EQUATIONS OF THE PRESENTEEISM AND ABSENTEEISM CONSTRUCTS

Presenteeism	
Work and Job Context - Negativity = $0.50 * \text{Presenteeism}$, Errorvar. = 0.75, $R^2 = 0.25$	
(0.019)	(0.058)
26.53	12.96
Work and Job Context - Resistance = $0.30 * \text{Presenteeism}$, Errorvar. = 0.71, $R^2 = 0.21$	
(0.012)	(0.097)
3.15	10.34
Physical Health - Negativity = $1.08 * \text{Presenteeism}$, Errorvar. = 0.17, $R^2 = 0.39$	
(0.018)	(0.047)
19.53	13.26
Physical Health - Resistance = $0.23 * \text{Presenteeism}$, Errorvar. = 0.95, $R^2 = 0.18$	
(0.015)	(0.053)
21.94	12.03
Absenteeism	
Personal Issues = $0.80 * \text{Absenteeism}$, Errorvar. = 0.37, $R^2 = 0.63$	
(0.025)	(0.066)
31.69	5.52
Work-Related Issues = $0.51 * \text{Absenteeism}$, Errorvar. = 0.73, $R^2 = 0.27$	
(0.042)	(0.065)
54.33	11.23

Source: Own calculations.

A review of Table 6 yields many implications. As these two constructs were distinctively analyzed, it would be convenient to examine these implications one-by-one. The participating mid-level managers emphasize the negative side of presenteeism, i.e., both

the contributions and coefficients of determination that belong to the negativities are greater than the contributions and coefficients of the resistances. This finding is therefore in harmony with the aforementioned literature that posits that presenteeism is an unfavorable aspect of well-being. Furthermore, it is also noteworthy that physical health is focused on more than work and the job context in terms of negativities. That is, the participants state that their problems with their physical health are a greater undesirable component in terms of their presenteeism. When absenteeism is checked, an intriguing implication is that the managers attribute their personal issues to make them off or attend to work poorly much more strongly than work issues. However, they still agree with the idea that both personal and work-related issues are the reasons for their absenteeism. A surprising similarity between these two constructs is the strong stress on oneself. The managers primarily indicate their own physical health negativities for presenteeism and personal issues for absenteeism; work and job matters are secondary. This commonality is also thought to be consistent with the literature, as private issues, especially health, are claimed to be a common cause for both presenteeism and absenteeism.

The remaining two constructs, job alienation and job dissatisfaction, were also confirmed via distinct uses of second-level modeling. Figure 3 presents the preliminary evidence, again, with the t-values.

FIGURE 3. SECOND-LEVEL FACTOR MODELING FOR JOB ALIENATION AND JOB DISSATISFACTION WITH t-VALUES

Note: JA: Job Alienation; JA_BO: Business Oriented; JA_TO: Task Oriented; JD: Job Dissatisfaction; JD_JTC: Job and Task Challenges; JD_E: Equality Problems. Please see Tables 2 and 4 for the item abbreviations.

Source: Own calculations.

The next step was similar to the steps of the two previous constructs examined. Table 7 posits that the second-level job alienation and job dissatisfaction constructs are overall distinctively realistic if some of the prominent goodness-of-fit statistics are considered.

TABLE 7. GOODNESS-OF-FIT STATISTICS FOR THE JOB ALIENATION AND JOB DISSATISFACTION CONSTRUCTS

CRITERION	ACCEPTED LIMITS*	VALUES	RESULT
RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation)	Good fit: RMSEA<0.05	Job Alienation: 0.196	Unacceptable fit.
	Acceptable fit: 0.05≤RMSEA≤0.1	Job Dissatisfaction: 0.008	Good fit.
GFI (Goodness of Fit Index)	Good fit: 0.95≤GFI≤1.00	Job Alienation: 0.99	Good fit.
	Acceptable fit: 0.9<GFI<0.95	Job Dissatisfaction: 1.00	Good fit.
AGFI (Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index)	Good fit: 0.95≤AGFI≤1.00	Job Alienation: 0.98	Good fit.
	Acceptable fit: 0.9<AGFI<0.95	Job Dissatisfaction: 0.99	Good fit.
CFI (Comparative Fit Index)	0.90≤CFI	Job Alienation: 0.99	Good fit.
		Job Dissatisfaction: 1.00	Good fit.
SRMR (Standardized Root Mean Square Residual)	SRMR<0.05	Job Alienation: 0.048	Good fit.
		Job Dissatisfaction: 0.027	Good fit.

Note: * Diamantopoulos & Sigauw (2000); Schermelleh-Engel, Moosbrugger, & Müller (2003).

As for the last step, the two constructs' structural equations that are screened in Table 8 were investigated, and the participants' positions regarding their job alienation and dissatisfaction were discussed.

TABLE 8. STRUCTURAL EQUATIONS OF THE JOB ALIENATION AND JOB DISSATISFACTION CONSTRUCTS

Job Alienation	
Business Oriented = 0.71*Job Alienation, Errorvar. = 0.50, R ² = 0.50	
(0.087)	(0.042)
81.90	11.85
Task Oriented = 1.37*Job Alienation, Errorvar. = 0.88, R ² = 0.26	
(0.093)	(0.082)
144.47	18.41
Job Dissatisfaction	
Job and Task Challenges = 0.32*Job Dissatisfaction, Errorvar. = 0.90, R ² = 0.10	
(0.017)	(0.064)
18.44	14.06
Equality Problems = 0.24*Job Dissatisfaction, Errorvar. = 0.94, R ² = 0.17	
(0.027)	(0.090)
8.80	10.47

Source: Own calculations.

According to Table 8, the mid-level managers consider that their tasks are the primary reason that underlies their job alienation and that their business context is also an effective component. That is, the managers consider that their management duties could vigorously boost their withdrawal tendencies from business issues, while the features of the business context are a lesser boosting factor. A distinct investigation of the managers' job dissatisfaction reveals that their ideas about the extent to which they are being unequally treated and the general features and difficulties of what they do are encouraging factors of the dissatisfaction - the managers are discontented about these issues. A related red flag is the strength of the connections (the coefficients of determination) between these two

factors and this dissatisfaction; the managers could have the opinion that there could be better indicators if their job dissatisfaction is emphasized.

4.3. Main study: model testing and findings

The findings of the pilot study demonstrated the valid and reliable statistical structures of each subject considered with the data from 263 participating mid-level managers. Following this, the first part of the main study proved that it was statistically valid and, moreover, convenient to consider second-level factor models for each distinctive subject via the investigation of the data collected from more than 2,000 participants.

FIGURE 4. DETAILED RESEARCH MODEL WITH t-VALUES

Note: PRESENT: Presenteeism; P_WJC_N: Work and Job Context - Negativity; P_WJC_R: Work and Job Context - Resistance; P_PH_N: Physical Health - Negativity; P_PH_R: Physical Health - Resistance; ABS: Absenteeism; A_PI: Personal Issues; A_WRI: Work-Related Issues; JA: Job Alienation; JA_BO: Business Oriented; JA_TO: Task Oriented; JD: Job Dissatisfaction; JD_JTC: Job and Task Challenges; JD_E: Equality Problems. Please see Tables 1-4 for the item abbreviations.

Source: Own calculations.

As for the last step in the analysis process, the proposed research model in Figure 1 was tested. With the outcomes obtained so far, it was possible to denote the model in more detail. Therefore, the detailed research model that also involves the t-values is given in Figure 4.

A clear outcome from Figure 4 is that there is no significance problem at 5%. This urged an investigation of the overall model; accordingly, some chief goodness-of-fit statistics denoted in Table 9 were checked. The result was the implication of a realistic model.

TABLE 9. GOODNESS-OF-FIT STATISTICS FOR THE RESEARCH MODEL

CRITERION	ACCEPTED LIMITS*	VALUE	RESULT
RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation)	Good fit: $RMSEA < 0.05$ Acceptable fit: $0.05 \leq RMSEA \leq 0.1$	0.052	Acceptable fit.
GFI (Goodness of Fit Index)	Good fit: $0.95 \leq GFI \leq 1.00$ Acceptable fit: $0.9 < GFI < 0.95$	0.97	Good fit.
AGFI (Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index)	Good fit: $0.95 \leq AGFI \leq 1.00$ Acceptable fit: $0.9 < AGFI < 0.95$	0.96	Good fit.
CFI (Comparative Fit Index)	$0.90 \leq CFI$	1.00	Good fit.
SRMR (Standardized Root Mean Square Residual)	$SRMR < 0.05$	0.063	Unacceptable fit.

Note: * Diamantopoulos & Sigua (2000); Schermelleh-Engel, Moosbrugger, & Müller (2003).

The evidence in Figure 2 and Table 9 points out that there are indeed significant relationships among the unwell-being factors of the mid-level managers regarding their business context. This is considered to be an important preliminary finding as these managers work in the largest businesses in Turkey. Moreover, this fact was an encouraging issue to scrutinize the details of the model. The first detail concerned the structural equations, which are given in Table 10.

In the first phase, all the constructs were distinctively confirmed as second-level latent variables. This time, in the current phase, these constructs were combined within the research model, and it was expected that there could be some changes in the nature of the structural equations due to the overall interactions. Because of this possibility, an appropriate approach would be to discuss the model's structural equations given in Table 10 and simultaneously compare these to the equations exhibited in Tables 6 and 8 regarding the confirmations.

According to Table 10, the participating mid-level managers still predicate personal issues as the primary source of their absenteeism rather than work-related issues. It is, therefore, conclusive that the participants tend to act professionally, i.e., they do not perceive work-related unfavorableness as being a strong excuse to leave work temporarily for their personal problems. It is also noteworthy that this situation does not change whether absenteeism is considered to be a distinct construct (see Table 6) or whether it is involved in the integrative model as an agent of interaction.

TABLE 10. STRUCTURAL EQUATIONS OF THE RESEARCH MODEL TESTED

Personal Issues = 0.75*Absenteeism, Errorvar. = 0.44, R ² = 0.56	(0.0097)	(0.055)
	77.34	7.93
Work-Related Issues = 0.55*Absenteeism, Errorvar. = 0.70, R ² = 0.30	(0.0059)	(0.038)
	92.88	18.59
Business Oriented = 0.99*Job Alienation, Errorvar. = 0.28, R ² = 0.87	(0.0069)	(0.033)
	142.32	10.85
Task Oriented = 0.98*Job Alienation, Errorvar. = 0.31, R ² = 0.83	(0.0063)	(0.040)
	156.65	5.78
Job and Task Challenges = - 0.71*Job Dissatisfaction, Errorvar. = 0.49, R ² = 0.51	(0.0033)	(0.14)
	-23.73	3.44
Equality Problems = - 0.11*Job Dissatisfaction, Errorvar. = 0.99, R ² = 0.012	(0.0046)	(0.078)
	-21.79	12.59
Work and Job Context - Negativity = 0.75*Presenteeism, Errorvar. = 0.43, R ² = 0.57	(0.0082)	(0.034)
	92.21	12.65
Work and Job Context - Resistance = - 0.21*Presenteeism, Errorvar. = 0.95, R ² = 0.045	(0.0051)	(0.074)
	-41.73	12.90
Physical Health - Negativity = 0.68*Presenteeism, Errorvar. = 0.53, R ² = 0.47	(0.0083)	(0.052)
	82.59	10.36
Physical Health - Resistance = 0.045*Presenteeism, Errorvar. = 1.00, R ² = 0.0020	(0.0043)	(0.10)
	10.48	9.78

Source: Own calculations.

In terms of job alienation, there is a slight difference. The two unfavorable dimensions related to business and tasks still boost job alienation; nevertheless, as a distinct construct (Table 8), tasks play a greater role, whereas both business environment and task problems equally encourage the managers' job alienation once it is integrated into the model (Table 10). A possible reason for this difference is believed to originate from the interactions within the model. The managers could have perceived that their management tasks were uniform in their essence and therefore considered these tasks as tedious and burdensome issues with no further feeling of accomplishment. This perception is stronger than the negative feelings towards one's own business if job alienation is scrutinized alone (Table 8). In contrast, the interactions with the other unwell-being factors in the research model bring the business context to the surface, as work and job-related issues are mentioned frequently (Table 10); thus, this mentioning could have also caused the promotion of business problems when the managers' job alienation is in question.

The managers are all consistent when their presenteeism is investigated. A solitary consideration of presenteeism shows that the negative dimensions are better actors compared to the contrary dimensions of resistance (Table 6). The integration of this factor into the research model reiterates this outcome; accordingly, the resistance dimensions

pose very weak connections to presenteeism (Table 10). The managers simply dwell on negativities if the subject is their presenteeism. However, a slight change is observed between the distinct and integrated investigations of presenteeism. The mid-level managers emphasize the problems with their physical health more than the problems caused by their work and job context if presenteeism is questioned separately (Table 6) and vice versa when it is embedded into the model (Table 10). The first issue that appears about this switch is the aforesaid interactions; thus, the related gradual surfacing of the business context could be an underlying reason.

The structural equations for the participants' job dissatisfaction indicate a great change across Tables 8 and 10. An isolated investigation denoted in Table 8 reveals that the components, job and task challenges and equality problems are positive contributors to the participants' job dissatisfaction, albeit by means of weak connections. In contrast, the integration of dissatisfaction into the model concludes that both components weaken it (Table 10). In the meantime, this integration reveals that the managers' perceived equality problems have very weak connections to their job dissatisfaction, which suggests that they barely consider these problems to be a dissatisfaction element when all unwell-being factors are considered aggregately. The other element, job and task challenges, has a negative contribution to the participants' job dissatisfaction via a moderate relationship. Apparently, the participating mid-level managers could be expecting to be outfaced and even accepting of it by what they do in their businesses. As this implication is possible when the integration is present, a reason could be the strong emphasis on the business context and the reflection of this emphasis on job dissatisfaction, much like the aforementioned previous reason. This is considered to be another sign of professionalism as the managers tend to keep away from sentiency in the form of inequality beliefs in the business context and instead prefer to address the challenges that are presented by their jobs and tasks.

A summary of the findings and implications from Table 10 points out that the mid-level managers of the largest businesses in Turkey consider work-related issues to be a weak excuse for not attending to work properly. They posit that both business and task issues play equal roles in boosting their withdrawal tendencies from the work context and strongly emphasize the negative sides of both the work and job context and their personal health for their unwilling presence and tasking in their businesses. Meanwhile, they almost ignore their perceptions about being treated unfairly during tasking, and they are ready and eager to cope with their job and task challenges.

A final and brief comparison between the isolated confirmations of the constructs (in Tables 6 and 8) and their investigations within the integrative model (Table 10) implies that the managers tend to focus on their personal matters while each construct is scrutinized distinctively, and this tendency switches to business context issues partially within the integrative model because these issues are mentioned significantly throughout the overall interactions. A general implication across the distinctive and integrative investigations of the constructs is the emphasis on professionalism; the managers are liable to refrain from dispraising their businesses to a large extent although the subject is their unwell-being in relation to their business context. At the same time, they speculate that their personal matters could also be a reason for their aforesaid unwell-being .

The final investigation involved the details of the interactions among the four unwell-being factors, and Table 11 shows the related correlations.

TABLE 11. CORRELATION MATRIX OF THE UNWELL-BEING FACTORS

	PRESENTEEISM	JOB DISSATISFACTION	JOB ALIENATION	ABSENTEEISM
PRESENTEEISM	1.00			
JOB DISSATISFACTION	-0.08 (0.01) -61.48	1.00		
JOB ALIENATION	0.62 (0.00) 244.29	-0.13 (0.02) -64.27	1.00	
ABSENTEEISM	0.75 (0.00) 176.23	-0.11 (0.02) -62.64	0.92 (0.00) 252.29	1.00

Source: Own calculations.

A direct result from Table 11 is that the managers' unwell-being factors indeed interact with one another. This is a spectacular outcome on many grounds. It is now clear that the participants exhibit signs of fatigue, task weariness and unwillingness and show withdrawal tendencies in their business contexts to a certain extent due to the aforesaid contextual problems and personal issues. Moreover, the participants conclude that these unfavorable aspects could covary; therefore, they need to be considered altogether in an integrative manner.

An examination of each interaction provides further insights. To start with, there is a positive and strong interaction between presenteeism and absenteeism: the managers simply consider unwilling tasking and temporary discontinuity simultaneously. This consideration is exactly consistent with the idea in the literature that these two factors are very close to one another; however, it is not a support for the idea that they are straight alternatives. A check between presenteeism and job alienation provides a similar result; the managers' unwillingness for and their withdrawal tendencies from the business context have positive relationships. That is, the perceptions about the lack of accomplishments and commitments despite the burdensome and unrewarding nature of the business context are accompanied by the reluctance to be and task in the same context. The literature is confirmed again in terms of the strong relationships between these two factors. An interesting outcome is the almost perfect interaction between job alienation and absenteeism, it is far stronger than the interaction between job alienation and presenteeism. An instant idea formed is that the managers prefer to leave the business temporarily rather than to continue to work unwillingly once they feel the need for the withdrawal. This idea also implies that the job alienation of the participants unearths their considerations about presenteeism and absenteeism to be indirect alternatives. In this case, the literature's claim about the alternativeness of presenteeism and absenteeism seems to be connoted by the outcomes reached. Finally, a glance of job dissatisfaction pinpoints extremely weak and negative interactions with the three other unwell-being factors. Previously, the job dissatisfaction construct posed some impotencies, i.e., it had positive but very weak connections to its components during the confirmation stage (Table 8); because job dissatisfaction is an integrated factor in the model, the course of connections reversed, and one of the components almost posed no connection at all (Table 10). Considering these findings, it was resolved that the managers could be barely addressing the job dissatisfaction construct as an unwell-being factor in an integrative manner and

that they could be looking for other issues for their job dissatisfaction. It is considered that Table 11 shows this resolve one more time: the participating mid-level managers seem to assign much less priority to their job dissatisfaction when it is mentioned among their other unwell-being factors.

5. Research limitations

This research had some limitations within two overlapping domains: design and application. As already mentioned, there was a unique and integrative model with an intent to find out how the unwell-being was structured with the contribution of the four factors. The design of the *contribution* had a great limitation due to the fact that there was no consensus in the literature as to how each factor would be connected with each other. This fact urged us to assume interactive and simultaneous connections. Moreover, an obvious limitation was about the *choice* of these factors; there were various possible factors that could make up the unwell-being, but only the ones that were frequently considered in scientific research were noted and added into the model, leaving the rest on shaky ground.

Other limitations were about the participants and their businesses. Due to easier access possibilities and the will of performing a homogeneous sampling, only mid-level managers provided their contributions for the research process. A further limitation was related to these mid-level managers' businesses; there are indeed countless businesses at the national level, but this study only dealt with those managers, who were actively taking part in the 500 biggest businesses of Turkey. Therefore, it is very convenient to state that both managers at other management levels and the rest of the businesses were ignored nationwide.

6. Conclusion and discussion

This study is concerned with the negative factors of the mid-level managers' work-related well-being who are working in the largest businesses in Turkey. To take an overall picture of these factors, i.e., to frame the participants' unwell-being within the business context, the literature was monitored. Presenteeism was the first such factor noted due to its unique intrinsic nature, scientific fame, and proof of connections to many other factors. The continuation of the literature review pointed out various factors; therefore, absenteeism, job alienation, and job dissatisfaction were the three other factors selected. Unlike the efforts to test the dyadic relationships between these factors, the main goal of this study was to analyze these factors' interactions within the domain of a proposed unique integrative unwell-being model.

The analyses revealed unprecedented findings and led to many conclusions. A noteworthy result was that the proposed model was validated. That is, the aforesaid mid-level managers agreed that they were facing these unfavorable factors simultaneously. It is, therefore, profoundly convenient to state that the managers face challenges that originate from their business environments and personal matters and that these challenges aggregately emerge as their unwell-being, which comprises the four integrative factors.

It was also interesting to see that most factors had positive interactions with the exception of the very weak interactions that belonged to job dissatisfaction; thus, the natures of the interactions were not uniform in the model. In addition, a comparison between the

managers' absenteeism and presenteeism via their interactions with job alienation implied a listing of preference. These two outcomes conclude that the managers accept all factors within the realm of their unwell-being, but they are not in agreement regarding the equal treatment of each factor. Briefly, they distinguish among the factors, although all factors fall in their unwell-being.

The ultimate conclusion is that the mid-level managers of the largest businesses in Turkey simultaneously consider both temporary avoidance from or irregular attendance at their work and tasking unwillingly in the business context. They perceive a lack of accomplishment and commitment although their work is challenging and unrewarding, and they show reluctance about being in their business context and tasking together with this perceived inadequacy. They prioritize temporary aloofness from their businesses rather than striving to continue tasking unwillingly because of their perceived need for withdrawal from the business context, and they consider that their job dissatisfaction is barely an indicator of their unwell-being compared to the other factors.

All stated conclusions necessitate some potential measures or active solutions to overcome the unwell-being problems of mid-level managers. These measures could target motivational boosts and work facilitations. A suggested example for financial motivation-building is the use of management-specific compensation that involves stock options or the exchange of stock options for cash rather than the traditional approaches of pay raises or bonuses. This suggestion is expected to be very motivational as it should be remembered that the managers are working in the largest businesses in Turkey. A suggested psychological motivator could be recognition; the managers should be individually celebrated by their employers upon achieving their tasks, and they should be given the chance to receive a personalized reward. Suggestions for more conventional psychological motivators could be their engagement in top-level decision-making processes and empowerment. In addition, suggested work facilitations include a greater emphasis on the managers' work-life balance, managerial job rotations, the determination of more reasonable and measurable goals, providing options for flexible working, and the appropriate use of professional teams that are formed by the managers to partially assume the burden of their tasks.

This is a preliminary study; therefore, there are many additional possible scientific suggestions, along with the aforesaid suggestions for practical purposes. Unwell-being was the combination of many related factors in this study, and these factors could thus be enriched in future research. For example, personal unfavorable issues, such as participants' stress or depression, and business-context issues, such as organizational silence, could be added to capture the mechanics of unwell-being more peripherally. Along with these additions, there could also be some variables that are effective on overall unwell-being. A simple idea indicates these variables to be demographical features and organizational culture, for instance. Another suggestion concerns the instruments considered. This study combined some instruments for each unwell-being factor's construct for a more inclusive measurement. Future combinations could be made by using general or specific instruments, depending on the research environment. A final suggestion involves the participants. The factors used could also apply to employees; therefore, their business context unwell-being could be an interesting topic to study.

A consideration of comparability extends these scientific suggestions much further. The participating managers' unwell-being in their business context was the issue, but there is also the opposite aspect: their well-being. An obvious suggestion, in this case, would be to

propose an integrative model to scrutinize the interactions among managers' well-being factors. Many factors on this other horizon, such as job satisfaction, organizational citizenship behavior, empowerment, and workplace spirituality, could be integrated in this new model. The next step could be comparisons among identical well-being and unwell-being models. Regardless of such comparisons, each one-way (either well-being or unwell-being-based) model could be compared to one another by using data from multiple levels of managers, managers from different sectors, and managers in identical or different types of businesses in different countries. This study provides a general understanding of Turkey's mid-level managers in terms of their business-related unwell-being, but a parallel international study would be a very positive contribution to the literature.

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